

A synonymous single nucleotide variant on the FAM20C gene causes non-lethal Raine syndrome

Bayram TORAMAN¹, İdris ER², Burak Kaan KASAP³, Ümit UZUN⁴, Tuba DİNÇER⁵, Gökhan YILDIZ⁶,
Gülay KARAGÜZEL⁷, Saadettin KAYIPMAZ⁸ and Ersan KALAY⁹

1. Karadeniz Technical University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Medical Biology, Trabzon, Türkiye
2. Karadeniz Technical University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Medical Biology, Trabzon, Türkiye
3. Karadeniz Technical University, Institute of Health Sciences, Department of Medical Biology Trabzon, Türkiye
4. Karadeniz Technical University, Institute of Health Sciences, Department of Medical Biology Trabzon, Türkiye
5. Karadeniz Technical University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Medical Biology, Trabzon, Türkiye
6. Karadeniz Technical University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Medical Biology, Trabzon, Türkiye
7. Karadeniz Technical University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Paediatric Endocrinology and Diabetes, Trabzon, Türkiye
8. Karadeniz Technical University, Faculty of Dentistry, Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, Karadeniz Technical University, Faculty of Dentistry, Trabzon, Türkiye
9. Karadeniz Technical University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Medical Biology and Genetics, Trabzon, Türkiye

Corresponding Author.

Bayram TORAMAN

Phone: +90 506 338 0323

Mail: bayramtoraman@yahoo.com; btoraman@ktu.edu.tr

Supplementary Figure S1. The heterodimer space-filling model of FAM20C and FAM20A proteins was prepared by modifying the 5YH3 model. The Magnified representation of amino acids corresponds to the interface of the FAM20C and FAM20A complex (right). Some of the interacting FAM20C amino acids are shown in red. Visualized with Discovery Studio[®].

Supplementary Figure S2. AlphaFold3 multimer-predicted structures of FAM20C/FAM20A (A), hetero- and FAM20C/FAM20C (B) homo-dimers.

Supplementary Table S1. Decomposed the total Rosetta interface score into individual energy terms

Score Term	Description	WT (Weighted)	Mutant (Weighted)	Δ (Mutant – WT)
fa_atr (vdW)	Lennard-Jones attractive	-5350.69	-5210.89	+139.80
fa_rep atr (vdW)	Lennard-Jones repulsive (short-range clash)	+590.03	+608.87	+18.84
fa_sol	Solvation energy	+3492.89	+3470.95	-21.94
fa_intra_rep	Intra-residue repulsion	+157.38	+159.56	+2.18
fa_intra_sol_xover4	Intra-residue solvation (short-range)	+206.94	+207.16	+0.22
lk_ball_wtd	Orientation-dependent solvation	-141.38	-143.31	-1.93
fa_elec	Electrostatic interaction	-1164.59	-1145.79	+18.80
pro_close	Proline ring closure	+706.69	+679.31	-27.38
hbond_sr_bb	Backbone-backbone short-range H-bonds	-265.29	-243.98	+21.31
hbond_lr_bb	Backbone-backbone long-range H-bonds	-95.41	-96.86	-1.45
hbond_bb_sc	Backbone-sidechain H-bonds	-121.03	-111.34	+9.69
hbond_sc	Sidechain-sidechain H-bonds	-127.22	-130.59	-3.37
omega	Peptide bond planarity	+635.07	+663.64	+28.57
fa_dun	Sidechain rotamer preference	+2819.06	+2920.69	+101.63
p_aa_pp	Backbone torsion propensities	-92.23	-96.43	-4.20
yhh_planarity	Aromatic planarity	+1.81	+1.62	-0.19
ref	Reference energy (residue type)	+269.91	+275.03	+5.12
rama_prepro	Ramachandran preferences (pre-Proline)	+190.26	+213.78	+23.52
Total Score		1712.20	2021.42	+309.22

Interpretation Notes:

- Mutant structure has a **less favorable fa_atr** (less attractive van der Waals interaction).
- It also shows **higher total repulsion** and slightly reduced **H-bonding efficiency**.
- The **total score** (in REU) is significantly worse in the mutant, suggesting a less stable or disrupted interface.

Supplementary Table S2. Comparison of clinical features of previously reported cases with the present study

Clinical Findings	Present study	Elalaoui et al. [26]	Fradin et al. [27]	Rafaelsen et al. [28]	Simpson et al. [29]	Acevedo et al. [16]
Short stature	+	-	-	-	+	-
Consanguineous parents	+	+	+	-	+	+
Craniofacial dysmorphism	+	+	+	+	+	+
Hypertelorism	+	+	+	-	+	-
Exophthalmos / Proptosis	+	-	+	-	+	-
High-arched palate	+	+	+	-	+	+
Depressed nasal root / bridge	+	+	+	-	+	-
Anteverted nares / ears	+	-	+	-	+	-
Cleft palate	+	-	-	-	-	-
Brachydactyly	+	+	+	-	-	-
Midface hypoplasia	-	+	+	+	+	+
Prognathism / Micrognathia	+	+	+	-	+	+
Open bite malocclusion	+	+	-	-	-	+
Enamel hypoplasia / AI	+	+	+	+	+	+
Intracranial calcifications	-	+	+	+	+	+
Nephrocalcinosis	+	+	+	+	-	-
Osteosclerosis	-	-	-	+	+	-
Chiari malformation	+	-	-	-	-	-
Hearing impairment	-	-	-	-	+	+
Seizures	-	-	-	-	+	+

GO Biological Process 2023

Supplementary Figure S3. FAM20C GO biological process analysis results.

B

Supplementary Figure S4. Main text Fig. 2B raw blots. GST Pull Down Assay-Western Blot analysis of FAM20C-FAM20A heterodimer from pull-down samples and total protein

C

Supplementary Figure S5. Main text Fig. 2C raw blots. Ni-NTA Pull Down Assay-Western Blot analysis of FAM20C-FAM20C homodimer from pull-down samples and total protein. FAM20A was used as positive control in the final lane, as its interaction with FAM20C has been previously well-established in literature. FAM20A was used as positive control in the final lane, as its interaction with FAM20C has been previously well-established in literature.

Nucleus: DAPI
 GM130: Alexa 488
 FLAG: Alexa 647
 Scale Bar: 10 μm

Supplementary Figure S6. More confocal immunofluorescence images are shown.